

New complex compounds of ions with $3d^{7-10}$ electronic configuration with bidentate heterocyclic ligands (N, S) involved in electron-transfer processes

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Abstract : The synthesis and the structure of some new electron-transfer complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with heterocyclic ligands (N, S) of the naphthoquinone series are presented. The complex compounds are first characterized by elemental analysis, and then by IR, visible, UV and ESR spectra; conductometric and polarographic data were also taken into account. The results of these studies prove that the complexes are of the $[\text{M}-\text{N}_2\text{S}_2]^z$ type. Polarography in various solvents has established that the possible values for z are -2 , -1 and 0 . In order to get more information about the atoms involved in the coordination to the transition metal ions, a quantum-mechanical interpretation – based on the EHT-MO approach – has also been performed for the absorption bands of the free organic ligands and the complexes.

It is also worthy of pointing out that the synthesized compounds exhibit interesting biological properties.

Keywords : Electron transfer, heterocyclic ligands, transition metals.

The coordination chemistry has been considerably enriched during the last years as a result of the synthesis and characterization of new systems of complexes related by electron-transfer reactions¹ :

These studies revealed that, in such electron-transfer reactions, the oxidative stability of these complexes – having the same general composition and charge type – exhibits a marked dependence on the nature of the donor atoms.

The literature² mentions the important biologic-active, antiviral, tuberculostatic antimalaria and even antitumor properties of the ligands containing nitrogen and sulfur as donor atoms; the same properties are shown by the complexes that these ligands form with transitional metal ions (which act in the biological structures as essential microelements).

The importance of such compounds can be exemplified by the interesting biological activity associated with many 3-alkyl- and 3-alkenyl-substituted derivatives of 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone and arylamino-1,4-naphthoquinone. *o*-Amino-quinoid unit is present in many antibiotics such as actinomycin, mitomycin C, porfiromycin and streptonigrin.

With the view of extending the investigations about these kind of systems, the paper presents the synthesis and the properties of the complex compounds formed by Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} (acting in the biological structures as essential microelements) with two new naphthoquinonic ligands² containing X = S, Y = N as donor atoms, namely 2-acetamido-3-thio-1,4-naphthoquinone (**2**) and 2-acetamido-3-thiomethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**3**), denoted as AATNQ and AATMNQ respectively.

Results and discussion

The complexes obtained are microcrystalline colored

powders, air-stable, insoluble in ordinary organic solvents, sparingly soluble in dichloroethane and dioxane and soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The results of the elemental analysis show that these complexes are of the $[ML_2]$ type, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and $L = AATNQ$ and $AATMNQ$.

The chemical composition of these compounds leads to the conclusion that both AATNQ and AATMNQ act as bidentate ligands. Molar electric conductivity values ($0.86-2.03 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in 10^{-4} DMF solution, at 22 °C) show that all the complexes are non electrolytes, confirming the proposed formulation. This assumption has been confirmed by physico-chemical analyses and by a quantum-mechanical study as well.

Information regarding the nature of the chemical bond were obtained on the basis of the IR spectra⁴ for the free ligands and for the complex compounds. The data show that the absorption bands due to the vibration of various groups that are not involved in the coordination appear in the IR spectra of the free ligand and also in the ones of the complex compounds, in the same spectral regions, with uncharged or slightly modified intensities, because of the electromeric effects determined by the coordination.

The bands in the $3030-3150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, which is characteristic for ν_{NH_2} , appear in complexes at lower frequencies than in the ligands. The characteristic band of each ligand at 1360 cm^{-1} (ν_{C-N} , coupling NH_2) is displaced towards higher frequencies with a lower intensity. The changes suggest that the NH_2 group participates to the coordination. Very important for the discussion of the bond character is the band at 1220 cm^{-1} , in which the frequency for the C=S bond has an important contribution. In complexes, this band suffers a rough change in intensity. Sulfur atom participates as a donor atom. The band in the $630-680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ interval is also significant. Generally assigned to the C=S vibration, it appears with a much lower intensity in the complexes, proving the involvement of this group in the coordination. The metal complexes are also characterized by the appearance of some new bands of medium and low intensity at $580-560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $460-420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be assigned to ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-N} stretching frequencies, respectively.

Some data on the structure of the studied complexes were obtained by recording their visible and UV electronic spectra. Table 1 shows the absorption bands for the complexes and the assignments of some bands. The similarity between the electronic spectra of the new $[M-N_2S_2]$ com-

plexes and the electronic spectra of the square-planar complex ions⁵, suggests a similarity in their geometry.

Table 1. Electronic spectra and polarographic data of complex compounds

Compd.	$1/\lambda$ (cm^{-1})	Assignment	$E_{1/2}^a$ (V)	Couple
[Co(AATNQ) ₂]	16860	$^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$	-0.28	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	21580	$^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$	-0.53	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
			-1.04	quinone
[Ni(AATNQ) ₂]	21980	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$	-0.11	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	29240	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$	-0.48	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
	38000	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_u$	-0.97	quinone
[Cu(AATNQ) ₂]	14475	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$	-0.55	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	20600	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_u$	-0.80	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
	26500	$L \rightarrow M(CT)$	-1.05	quinone
[Zn(AATNQ) ₂]	22600	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*(L)$	-0.31	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	18600	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*(L)$	-0.64	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
			-1.00	quinone
[Co(AATMNQ) ₂]	16845	$^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$	-0.32	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	21600	$^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$	-0.64	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
			-1.10	quinone
[Ni(AATMNQ) ₂]	21840	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$	-0.20	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	29222	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$	-0.58	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
	37870	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_u$	-1.15	quinone
[Cu(AATMNQ) ₂]	14460	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$	-0.54	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	20480	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$	-0.68	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
	26650	$L \rightarrow M(CT)$	-1.20	quinone
[Zn(AATMNQ) ₂]	22450	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*(L)$	-0.35	$0 \leftrightarrow -1$
	18800	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*(L)$	-0.70	$-1 \leftrightarrow -2$
			-1.08	quinone

^acalomel reference electrode.

$10^{-1} M$ solution of tetra-*n*-butyl-ammonium perchlorate (as a supporting electrolyte).

A quantum-mechanical interpretation of the absorption bands proper to the free and coordinated ligands gives more information about the coordination.

The structural formula of each ligand has been modeled on the computer. Their molecular geometry has been optimized using the Molecular Mechanics approach (MM⁺), the cartesian coordinates of the atoms being used to perform EHT calculation⁶.

In the $[Ni-N_2S_2]$ complexes the first absorption band is assigned to an electron transfer involving an electron lone pair localized on the nitrogen atom. These transitions are displaced toward higher wavenumbers for the coordinated ligands as a consequence of the coordination. The shifts are caused by the mixing of the antibonding states with *d*-metal orbitals as well as to the lowering of the electron lone pairs energy that occurs after coordination. The last two bands are due to transitions between molecular orbitals practically localised on the oxygen atoms of naphthoquinone.

By comparing the spectra of the complex compounds with the ones of the free organic ligands, it shows that the first two bands are shifted, while the last two ones are not shifted, meaning that the oxygen atoms have nothing to do

with the coordination, which is realised by means of the sulfur and nitrogen atoms of the ligands.

Strong ESR spectra were obtained for $[\text{Ni-N}_2\text{S}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu-N}_2\text{S}_2]$. The $[\text{Ni}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$ has a spectrum consisting in three components.

It is suggested that the first two components ($g_{\perp} = 2.0178$, $g_{\parallel} = 2.0620$) originate in the splitting of the unpaired electron in the axial symmetry field of the complex, while the third one is the result of the donor-acceptor-type strong⁴¹ interaction between the ligand and the central ion ($g_{\parallel} = 2.0022$).

Fig. 1. The polarograms for $[\text{Co}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$ (1) and $[\text{Ni}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$ (2)

As far as $[\text{Cu}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$ is concerned, it presents a very intense ESR spectrum, with anisotropic parameters $g_{\perp} = 2.0706$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.2408$ in agreement with the d^9 electronic configuration for Cu^{II} in this square-planar complex.

In the polarograms of the studied compounds (Table 1), three polarographic half-wave potentials appear – as shown in Fig. 1, for $[\text{Co}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$.

This fact proves the existence of several reduced species in solution and also that at the dropping mercury electrode the reduction of the neutral and monoanionic species occurs, according to the general equation :

The data obtained about these complex compounds show that these species can also be chemically synthesized (apart from the synthesis from one another), taking into account the fact that the half-potential range (between -0.11 V and -1.15 V) is one in which the reducing or oxidizing agents cannot tear the complex apart.

The $[\text{M-N}_2\text{S}_2]^z$ system (where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{L} = \text{AATNQ}$ and AATMNQ) provides five-membered chelate rings; over each of these rings, the electrical charge seems to be delocalized to some extent, consequently increasing the stability of such a coordination compound.

Moreover, the biological activity of these new ligands and complexes has been investigated, in order to enrich this study. It was tested for AATNQ, AATMNQ and their complexes described above by using them (100 mg/l in DMSO) against various microbes, germs and bacteria. The best results were obtained against *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphilococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, by means of the filter paper disk method. The chemical compounds were all proved to be highly or moderately active (to be more specific, the inhibition zones have been found between 20 mm and 32 mm (including the diameter of the disk, which was 6 mm)). It is to stress out that, without any exception, the biological activity of the complexes are better than the one of the free organic ligands. By comparing to one another the complexes formed by the same ligand with different metal ions, the biological activity increases in the following order : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$.

Conclusions :

The correlation of the elemental chemical analyses with the results of the physico-chemical and quantum-mechanical investigation suggest that the new complexes described in this paper are of the $[\text{M-N}_2\text{S}_2]$ -type, where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II} . This formulation is supported by the IR spec-

tral analyses, which confirm that AATNQ and AATMNQ act as bidentate ligands having both nitrogen and sulfur as donor atoms, as shown below :

The electronic and ESR spectra of these complexes lead to the conclusion that they exhibit a center-symmetrical square-planar geometry. Polarographic data prove their involvement in the electron-transfer processes.

The biological tests provided for these compounds, by using the filter paper disk method, show an interesting activity against various microorganisms.

Experimental

Reagents : All the chemicals we used were analytical grade : $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck a.p.), $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck a.p.),

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck a.p.), ZnCl_2 (Fluka A.G. a.p.), AATNQ (double recrystallized) and AATMNQ (double recrystallized).

Instruments : The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 Hewlett Packard instrument. An Unicam UV-visible 2-300 spectrophotometer was used to perform the electronic spectra, which were obtained in 10^{-3} M acetone solutions. The ESR spectra were recorded with an IFA Bucharest AR 7-5 spectrometer, working in the X band (9060 MHz) and having a 100 kHz modulation of the magnetic field. The polarograms were recorded with an Orion KTS 7-77-4/b instrument. The half-wave potentials of the solutions (10^{-3} M) of complexes were measured at room temperature, using a calomel reference electrode and a dropping mercury electrode; a 10^{-1} M solution of tetra-*n*-butyl-ammonium perchlorate was used as supporting electrolyte (as mentioned above). The electrical conductivity of the complexes was measured (in 10^{-4} M DMF solutions, at 22 °C) on a Radelkis OK-102/1 conductivity-meter, the cell constant being 0.897 cm^{-1} .

General procedure : In order to prepare the $[\text{Ni}(\text{AATNQ})_2]$, a solution of ligand (0.92 g) dissolved in a minimal amount of absolute ethanol was added under continuous stirring to a solution of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5 g) in 25 mL absolute ethanol. A deep-red fine crystalline precipitate immediately was formed. One kept on stirring for two hours

at room temperature. The product was isolated by filtration, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under vacuum.

The other complexes have been prepared in a similar manner.

References

1. E. S. Raper, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **129**, 91; E. S. Raper, J. R. Creighton and W. Clegg, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1995, **87**, 237; V. Mureşan, L. S. Sbirna, A. Reiss and N. Mureşan, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1997, **42**, 193; V. Mureşan, A. Reiss, L. S. Sbirna and N. Mureşan, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 2034; V. Mureşan, L. S. Sbirna, S. Sbirna, C. I. Lepa datu and N. Mureşan, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2001, **48**, 439; N. Mureşan, L. S. Sbirna, S. Sbirna, V. Mureşan and C. I. Lepa datu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 412; V. Mureşan, S. Sbirna, C. I. Lepa datu, L. S. Sbirna and N. Mureşan, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2002, **49**, 447; T. H. Tseng and Y. J. Lee, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **47**, 1165.
2. P. Truitt, F. Mahon, R. L. Hall and T. E. Eris, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 962; N. P. Buu-Hoi, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1944, **11**, 578; K. W. Rao, K. Biemann and A. Woodward, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **35**, 2532; R. F. Fandy, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **48**, 795; A. K. Khalafallah, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **48**, 801.
3. N. Mureşan, S. Sbirna, and L. S. Sbirna (under press).
4. B. Hutchinson, D. Eversdyk and S. Olbrich, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1974, **30**, 1605; K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Electronic Spectra", John Wiley, New York, 1963, p. 315.
5. H. B. Gray and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **35**, 260; A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectra", Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 503.
6. G. Calzaferri and M. Brande, *OPCE Bulletin*, 1992, **12**, 73.